

Local String Transduction as Sequence Labeling

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Abstract

We show that the general problem of string transduction can be reduced to the problem of sequence labeling. While character deletions and insertions are allowed in string transduction, they do not exist in sequence labeling. We show how to overcome this difference. Our approach can be used with any sequence labeling algorithm and it works best for problems in which string transduction imposes a strong notion of locality (no long range dependencies). We experiment with spelling correction for social media, OCR correction, and morphological inflection, and we see that it behaves better than seq2seq models and yields state-of-the-art results in several cases.

1 Introduction

String transduction (mapping one string to another) is an essential ingredient in the natural language processing (NLP) toolkit that helps solve problems ranging from morphological inflection (Dreyer et al., 2008) and lemmatization to spelling correction (Cotterell et al., 2014), text normalization (Porta and Sancho, 2013) and machine translation (Kumar et al., 2006).

Finite-state technology is often used with string transduction (Allauzen et al., 2007), especially when there is a strong notion of locality in the transduction problem, i.e., when there are no long range dependencies between the predicted characters. More recently, neural network methods have become more common for such problems using the seq2seq models that were introduced for machine translation (Bahdanau et al., 2015).

Similarly, sequence labeling algorithms have been the mainstay for an array of problems in NLP, including part-of-speech tagging, named entity recognition and semantic role labeling. Various models have been proposed to do sequence labeling, including conditional random fields, hidden Markov models and neural networks.

String transduction and sequence labeling are often treated as two separate entities, and indeed, usually give treatment to different problems in NLP. We claim and show that there is a great similarity between them, and that one can be reduced to the other.

Sequence labeling is often associated with a set of problems in which the set of labels is small compared to the vocabulary. Still, this labeling essentially associates each symbol (usually a word) in a sequence (usually a sentence) with a label. As such, it can be seen as a specific case of string transduction that imposes a one-to-one correspondence between input and output symbols. This is the easier side of the reduction between sequence labeling and string transduction, and it has been exploited in the deep learning literature with seq2seq models.

In this paper, we come to address the reduction in the reverse direction – i.e. *we show how to frame string transduction as sequence labeling*. We do this by decomposing the transduction process into two parts: first, we induce an alignment between the characters of the input and output strings and then we use a sequence labeling model to predict the final output of the string.

The main difficulty here is not in the size of the vocabulary compared to the label set, but the fact that string transduction can yield to arbitrary output string length compared to the input string. In machine

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translation, for example, a classic example of string transduction, the sentence in the target language can be shorter, longer, and contain a significant amount of re-ordering. Indeed, re-ordering is a challenge with string transduction. A sequence labeling model usually maintains higher order of monotonicity (such as with Markovian models), while for general string transduction problems, one needs models such as encoder-decoders or grammatical models. Such expressive models, on the other hand, are *not* a good fit for string transduction problems with a strong notion of locality, as they are too complex and lead to weaker generalization power for such problems (Rastogi et al., 2016). We show this weakness in our experiments with seq2seq models supporting similar conclusions in previous work such as by Schnober et al. (2016). Our experiments show that even when seq2seq models are incorporated with hard monotonic attention (Aharoni and Goldberg, 2017), our reduction to sequence labeling outperforms such models on certain problems with a strong notion of locality.

Our approach to reduce string transduction to sequence labeling relies on a simple observation: in most cases in transduction, it is easier to *delete* a symbol than to *insert* a symbol. This is true because insertion requires identifying both the point of insertion and the character that needs to be inserted, while deletion is a “binary” decision – either the decoding algorithm chooses to delete a specific symbol or not to. A similar observation was made by Schnober et al. (2016), Rosca and Breuel (2016) and Chandlee (2014) and is also present in much earlier work by Koskenniemi (1983) and later in Chandlee (2014). String transduction is treated by Koskenniemi (1983) as a two-layer problem: two strings (a surface representation and a lexical representation) were aligned according to a set of “two-layer” handwritten rules. In this paper, we propose a similar setup to Koskenniemi’s but instead, we use various sequence labeling methods to automatically create these alignments (instead of hand-engineer them). This is possible by considering the three character operations used in string transduction – *deletions*, *insertions* and *substitutions* – as tagging operations. While Koskenniemi’s work was done only in the context of morphology, we extend the idea further and apply it to a wider set of problems. However, our approach, like Koskenniemi’s, is for now limited to character level tasks.

Our observation leads to an approach which is simple, yet powerful. We explain it in §3 and then perform an extensive experimentation with it in various scenarios, comparing it to models such as seq2seq. We test our approach thoroughly on three string transduction problems with a strong notion of locality: social media spelling correction, optical character recognition and morphological inflection. Each problem is tested with several sequence labeling algorithms. In all cases, we find that our approach is competitive with strong baselines and in some cases outperforms them. Our approach is independent of the sequence labeling algorithm that is used, and indeed we experiment with it in conjunction with four different sequence labeling learning algorithms.

2 Problem Formulation

We give a treatment to the problem of string transduction. Given an input alphabet, Σ , an output alphabet Λ , and training data, we aim to learn a function $f: \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Lambda^*$ that maps input strings to output strings. The training data comes in the form of pairs of strings $(x^{(i)}, y^{(i)})$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, M\}$. Note that the input string and output string can be of different length.

We reduce the problem of learning f to sequence labeling. With sequence labeling, we aim to learn a function $g: \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Lambda^*$ such that the length of $y = g(x)$ is the same as of x . This means that the training data we receive to learn g has input and output strings of the same length. With sequence labeling, $g(x)$ is referred to as the “labels” of x , as each element in x is mapped to a single element in $g(x)$ (elements from the input string are not deleted and new ones are not inserted).

Clearly, the problem of string transduction subsumes the problem of sequence labeling, as one can always try to learn a mapping f from a given training data of strings of identical length. However, there is a significant distinction that is usually made between the two, as string transduction can re-write a string into a completely different string, while sequence labeling has a stronger notion of locality.

As such, sequence labeling is considered an easier problem than general string transduction. Yet, we show in this paper how to exploit sequence labeling algorithms, with their flexibility and efficiency, to do general string transduction.

3 Transduction as Insertion and Labeling

Most approaches to string transduction involve inducing an alignment between symbols in the input and output strings (Knight and Graehl, 1998; Clark, 2001; Eisner, 2002; Azawi et al., 2013; Bailly et al., 2013). In an alignment, unaligned input symbols are called deletions, while unaligned output symbols are called insertions.

It is challenging to jointly induce alignments and learn a transduction model.

A second challenge is that, at prediction time, it is difficult to predict the insertions, as there can be an arbitrary number of them between any two input symbols. The prediction problem would be much simpler if the insertion positions were in place, because the model would only need to decide which symbol goes in each position.

Our approach is based on this idea. We decompose the transduction process into first predicting insertion positions in the input string, and then labeling the modified input string to produce the final output string. The insertion function might predict insertion positions that should not be there —we call these *spurious* insertions. In this case we rely on the labeling function to eliminate these spurious insertions. It is an easier task to *delete* a symbol than to *insert* one for string transduction. Therefore, marking the potential insertions in the string and then deleting them if necessary during decoding reduces the problem of string transduction to sequence labeling and as such allows using the Viterbi algorithm for decoding.¹ In addition, to avoid the challenge of inducing alignments, our approach relies on existing ones — for our experiments, we use the edit distance algorithm. From these initial alignments, our approach learns an insertion function and a sequence labeler, which perform string transduction when composed. This simple approach is also very flexible, because potential insertions can later be deleted. We found this approach to yield quite good alignments, as the accuracy of our algorithm when the alignment is *known* is quite high and supersedes state-of-the-art results in several cases. We now explain this technique more in detail.

3.1 Insertion Algorithm

We learn an “insertion context function” $\sigma: \mathbb{N} \times \Sigma^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. Given a string $x = x_1 \cdots x_k$ over Σ and an index in that string (between 0 and k),² this function tells how many *potential* insertions could happen in that position.

For example, say we would like to transduce the string `say` from its base form to its past form `said`. The insertion context function might learn that there needs to be an insertion following the `y` that corresponds to the `d`. Therefore, the insertion function values for `say` would be:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma(i, \text{say}) &= 0 & \forall i \in \{0, 1, 2\} \\ \sigma(3, \text{say}) &= 1.\end{aligned}$$

and therefore the string we would try to transduce to `said` would be the string `say ϵ` , where ϵ is a special symbol marking potential insertion.

Learning σ To learn σ , we use the following procedure. We first align each pair of strings in the training set using an algorithm such as edit distance (see §4.1). We then check for all contexts in which an insertion, or a sequence of insertions happen. A context is defined to be the preceding character before the sequence of insertions and the character that follows the sequence of insertions – for instance, in the previous example `say`, the context for the letter `a` would be the letters `s` and `y`. All of these contexts are added to a dictionary of insertion contexts, always keeping the maximal number of insertions for each specific context. Then the function σ adds a sequence of insertions any time a specific context fires. For the example above, the context we learn is `y ϵ $` where `$` denotes the end of a string. Therefore, for a

¹Finite state transducers that allow insertions or deletions, in practice, need to bound the number of insertions at any specific point, similarly to our insertion context function. This is done by operating on a lattice, where a path in that lattice corresponds to a string transduction with a specific alignment. Decoding using a lattice is equivalent to using the Viterbi algorithm. See, for example, Rastogi et al. (2016).

²The index really marks a *space* between two characters in the string, with 0 denoting the beginning of the string.

Figure 1: Graphical depictions of BiLSTMs (left), conditional random fields (middle) and refinement hidden Markov models (right). In practice, for the R-HMMs and CRFs we use a trigram model and not a bigram model as depicted.

decoded string that has the same context as the one found before, for instance, the string `slay` we would have $\sigma(4, \text{slay}) = 1$.

For all contexts, we calculate (based on the training data) a frequency table, that gives the probability of an insertion given the specific context. In some cases, we then tune a threshold (based on a development set) so that we add insertions only in cases where the frequency is larger than that threshold. We found out that while it perhaps prevents insertions in legitimate positions, if the frequency threshold is low enough, it does not have an adverse effect. On the contrary, it prevents adding spurious insertions that cannot be correctly recovered as deletions. For more details, see §4.

In the morphology tasks we experiment with, insertions tend to happen as suffixes or prefixes. To capture this, we also learn a pair of thresholds τ_0 and τ_1 (by grid search on the training set) such that $\sigma(i, x)$ is set to 0 if $\tau_0 \leq \frac{i}{|x|} \leq \tau_1$.

Learning the Labeling Model with σ Once we have the σ function applied to all aligned training data, we mark in the *output* sequences in the training data the spurious insertions that should not be in the input sequence with a special symbol \mathbb{D} (for deletion). Therefore, the learning algorithm is now also required to learn where to delete these extra insertions that σ elicits. For example, if we consider the previously mentioned example of `say` and `said`, the input sequence in this case would be `sayε` and the output sequence would be `said`. However, it is not always the case that the past tense of a verb with a *ay* ending is the same word root with the suffix *-d* (and the transformation of the final *y* to *i* to accommodate the new suffix). For example, the past tense of `may` is also `may`, and in this case, if the string `may` was also in the training set, `may` should retain its form and be transduced to `may`. With the context function mentioned above we would have the pair `mayε` (input sequence), `mayD` (output sequence) to learn from. During decoding, we apply the σ function on the input string and then remove the \mathbb{D} symbols from the string.

3.2 Sequence Labeling Models

We experiment with three models for sequence labeling: refinement hidden Markov models (R-HMMs; Stratos et al., 2013), conditional random fields (CRFs; Lafferty et al., 2001) and bidirectional Long Short Term Memory neural networks (biLSTMs; Graves and Schmidhuber, 2005). A graphical depiction of the models that we experiment with is given in Figure 1. For R-HMMs, we experiment with two learning algorithms, the expectation-maximization algorithm (EM; Dempster et al., 1977) and an L-PCFG spectral learning algorithm (Cohen et al., 2012; Cohen et al., 2013).³

4 Experiments

We describe in this section a set of experiments on datasets from three problems: social media spelling correction, optical character recognition (OCR) correction and morphological inflection. We believe that this array of datasets represents a broad set of problems in which string transduction as sequence

³We use the code from <https://github.com/shashiongithub/Rainbow-Parser>.

labeling can be tested. We apply the insertion technique to a set of sequence labelers: conditional random fields, refinement HMMs with expectation-maximization, spectral algorithms, and neural networks with biLSTM. All the results reported are at word level.

Our experiments require hyperparameter tuning of all algorithms, which we do over a fixed set of hyperparameters in the development set. For the latent-variable models, we vary the number of latent states between 1 and 48. For the biLSTM, we try a number of layers between 1 and 4 and a number of neurons ranging between 100 and 500.

The CRF is used with trigram modeling, and as such, the features it uses are very similar to the features used by the spectral algorithm. The main difference is that the spectral algorithm uses these features only during training, while the CRF uses them both during training and decoding.

In addition, we compare all our models to a seq2seq model implementation (Bahdanau et al., 2015). The model includes an attention mechanism, and we optimize the number of latent units over the development sets, ranging it from 10 to 100. We also include a comparison to seq2seq models with a “hard” attention mechanism (Aharoni and Goldberg, 2017), designed for string transduction with monotonic alignments.

4.1 Twitter Spelling Correction

In our first set of experiments, we use a corpus of spelling corrections for Twitter (Aramaki, 2010). The corpus includes 39,172 words in their original form and their correct form. We split this dataset into three parts (consecutively): 31,172 entries for a training set, 4,000 entries for a development set and another 4,000 entries for a test set.

Further Tuning In our experiments with EM and the spectral algorithm, we also tried to tune the σ context function on the development set. We discovered that the best context function is the one that adds ε slots for every context $a - b$ that appears in the data, if the relative frequency of $a - b$ to $a \star b$ is larger than $p = 0.0001$ (where \star stands for a wildcard; the interpretation of this relative frequency division is that we check whether the conditional probability of having an ε given the context $a \star b$ is larger than p). This is not particularly surprising given the fact that the Twitter dataset is composed of single words, each having a single typo. Therefore, each pair of misspelled and correctly spelled words often needs at most one insertion to be aligned. Even though this threshold may seem small, it was enough to remove all the isolated, non-representative context cases.

We try both a bigram and a trigram model. The trigram model greatly outperforms the bigram model, so we focus on it. We also did some preliminary experiments with a 4-gram model, but this model did not seem to do better than the trigram model. For the biLSTM architecture, we find on the development set that the smallest error is with 2 layers and 350 neurons.

In our experiments, we compare two latent-variable learning methods: the EM algorithm and the spectral algorithm described by Stratos et al. (2013). EM was run for 8 iterations – in some preliminary experiments where we ran EM for much longer, we noticed it converges after very few iterations. We then choose the iteration that gave the best result on the development set. We range the number of latent states, m , between 2 and 48.

The Dictionary Layer We also experiment with an additional layer that we add to our transduction algorithm. In this layer, we use a dictionary (a fixed set of words) for which we find the closest entry (in edit distance) to the output of our algorithm. In that case, our transduction algorithm can be thought of as producing an *intermediate* string, i.e., a string that may or may not already be a correct word but that is closer to the correct word in terms of edit distance. The intermediate string representation is intended to correct mistakes while actually relying on the type of substitutions, deletions and insertions done by users of social media. However, it is still prone to character-based mistakes, since it is a learned component. This is the reason why we also include the second edit distance layer.

We use two types of dictionaries. The first dictionary is the set of all correctly spelled words in the training data. The second dictionary is the English dictionary extracted from the GNU aspell software.⁴ In our results, we report four types of accuracy levels: the accuracy for the whole test set (where accuracy

⁴<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/gnu/aspell/dict/0index.html>.

method	acc	acc4+	acc6+	acc10+
aspell	30.1	41.1	56.6	82.6
train	40.1	59.6	71.6	71.9
GNU aspell	29.0	46.2	58.8	80.2
seq2seq	46.3	44.8	45.3	33.8
seq2seq+train	55.7	59.5	65.1	86.2
seq2seq+aspell	47.6	48.5	45.0	65.4
seq2seq (hard)	52.2	49.1	31.6	13.4
seq2seq+train (hard)	62.2	63.6	59.6	63.8
seq2seq+aspell (hard)	54.9	53.3	47.1	63.8
Spectral	54.3	52.6	44.0	28.1
Spectral+train	63.3	68.4	70.1	69.4
Spectral+aspell	56.6	59.4	58.6	70.2
biLSTM	54.1	54.1	55.4	49.3
biLSTM+train	64.6	64.6	68.7	72.1
biLSTM+aspell	56.9	57.0	59.1	63.0
CRF	34.2	34.2	32.2	19.0
CRF+train	55.9	55.9	59.5	67.8
CRF+aspell	45.2	45.2	46.4	50.8
EM	28.3	22.0	14.5	9.9
EM+train	52.8	64.0	70.8	72.7
EM+aspell	41.7	48.7	55.7	82.6

Table 1: Final results on the test set for the Twitter dataset. “aspell” stands for edit distance minimization using the aspell dictionary. “train” stands for the same with the dictionary extracted from the training set. “GNU aspell” stands for the results of running the GNU aspell software. “acc” denotes the accuracy over the whole dev/test set, “acc n +” for words of length $\geq n$. For each method the best model was chosen as follows: for CRF, over the dictionary; for EM, over iterations, number of latent states, and dictionary; and for spectral, over the hyperparameters, number of latent states and dictionary. The best model was chosen for each accuracy length criterion separately. The best result in each column is in bold. Top part are baselines. Bottom part uses our reduction to sequence labeling.

is measured as the number of words we fixed to the correct form), and also accuracy only for (correct) words which are longer than 4 characters, 6 characters and 10 characters.

We experimented with two types of edit distance algorithms. The first one allows only deletions, insertions and substitutions, and the other also allows transpositions. We discovered that edit distance with transposition behaves better, so we focus on it.

Results Table 1 gives the final result on the test set for the Twitter data (for different word lengths). The first thing to note is that there are some models that perform well on words longer than 10 characters. In general, it is easier to correct the spelling of longer words with the aspell dictionary because: (a) longer words are more likely to originate in words that appear in the dictionary; (b) there is more evidence in a long string for the misspelled string than in a short string.

Still, high accuracy on long words does not necessarily indicate the total accuracy is higher. We see that the spectral algorithm and the biLSTM model tend to give higher results on all words lengths overall than both the conditional random field and the EM algorithm. The GNU aspell software itself does not perform well on this dataset. This perhaps should not come as a surprise, as the GNU aspell software is designed for less informal text.

In addition, we see that sequence labeling performs consistently better than seq2seq models with attention. This should not come as a surprise, as seq2seq models encode the whole string before decoding it, even when the attention mechanism is used. This finding is also supported by (Schnober et al., 2016). The seq2seq method of Aharoni and Goldberg (2017) behaves even worse without using a dictionary,

context	dictionary	average	std
left	none	42.2	0.67
right	none	42.1	0.63
both	none	42.3	0.61
left	aspell	48.6	0.52
right	aspell	48.6	0.54
both	aspell	48.8	0.56
left	train	58.3	0.49
right	train	58.3	0.27
both	train	58.6	0.46

Table 2: Sensitivity analysis of the different context functions as a function of the probability threshold for insertion in a context. The contexts vary over left character (“left”), right character, or characters both on the left and the right (“both”). In addition, we use dictionaries (the aspell dictionary or the training data as dictionary). “average” gives the average result over the different thresholds, and “std” gives the standard deviation of that average.

especially for long words.

The Role of the Context Function We note that the choice of the context function is important, and extra ε symbols have to be added based on data-oriented choices. For example, when we experimented with a constant context function that adds an additional ε symbol after every character during training and decoding, the accuracy on the test set was much lower, whether we used a dictionary or not. To be more precise, the accuracy without using a dictionary was 33%, with the “train” dictionary mitigating the low performance to an accuracy of 61.1% (which is significantly lower than the biLSTM result and the spectral result) and 54.0% for the “aspell” dictionary.

To test the role of the context function, we further evaluated it more thoroughly. We created three types of context functions: one that looks at context only to the left of the current character, one that looks at context only on the right, and finally one that looks on context both on the left and on the right (as originally defined). In addition, we varied the threshold that activates an insertion in a specific context (see §3). The threshold was varied over the values in the set $\{0.0001, 0.0005, 0.001, 0.002, 0.005, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.2\}$. The higher the threshold is, the less spurious insertions happen (or insertions in general).

We experimented with a single learning algorithm: the biLSTM neural network. Table 2 summarizes this sensitivity analysis. The “average” results give the performance on the development set, averaging over the different thresholds. The “std” result gives the corresponding standard deviation. As can be seen, on average, right context functions have smaller standard deviation than other contexts, while the accuracy levels are similar for all contexts. In addition, there is relatively not a very large sensitivity to the actual threshold use.

The same dataset was also used by Cotterell et al. (2014) and by Silfverberg et al. (2016) though in both cases the results are not comparable as the experimental setup and the errors reported are different than the one used in this paper. For example, Cotterell et al. do not report accuracy at all, but instead plot mean edit distance as a function of the number of training examples.

4.2 Optical Character Recognition Correction

In our second set of experiments we used the Finnish OCR dataset used by Silfverberg et al. (2016). This corpus consists of 36,470 word pairs and it was generated from processing Early Modern Finnish texts through an OCR engine. According to Silfverberg et al. (2016) this corpus is a subset of a larger corpus comprising historical newspapers and magazines digitized by the National Library of Finland. This dataset has been both manually edited by the Institute of Languages of Finland as well as through crowdsourcing. In order to run our experiments we used the same setup and the same 10 non-overlapping parts described in Silfverberg et al. (2016).

Method	acc	acc4+	acc6+	acc10+
Unstructured	20.0	-	-	-
+ Lexicon	21.6	-	-	-
Perceptron	32.1	-	-	-
+ Lexicon	35.1	-	-	-
seq2seq	79.9	80.0	78.8	78.6
seq2seq (hard)	58.4	55.4	55.3	53.7
Spectral	77.3	77.9	76.3	73.8
CRF	81.8	81.9	80.7	78.8
EM	79.9	80.5	79.3	77.4
biLSTM	81.7	81.7	80.3	78.3

Table 3: Finnish OCR results. The first set of baselines (upper part) are reported by Silfverberg et al. (2016), and as such, the numbers are not available for all columns. Bottom part is our method.

Further Tuning In our experiments, we use 10-fold cross validation. The results are averaged over these ten folds. The hyperparameters for the spectral algorithm were tuned on the development set of the first fold, and then we used the hyperparameters identified at that phase for the rest of the folds.

We tuned the neural network architecture parameters on the development set of the first fold. We found out that the biLSTM model works best with 1 layer with 200 neurons.

We tuned the context function on development data again (for fold 1). We discovered that the best context function includes a pair of ε in any context of the form $a - - b$ that it appeared in the training data, and a single ε in any context with conditional probability larger than 0.0001. See more in §4.1. The OCR dataset is quite different in its structure from the Twitter dataset. It has both words that do not need any correction, and words in which more than one character was not labeled with the correct character. Another important difference is the fact the “typos” were often grammatical in the Twitter dataset (as they were human misspellings), while that is not the case in the OCR dataset. It is also worth noting that Finnish relies heavily on double letters in its spelling, which could explain why this choice of σ function works best in this case but not in the Twitter one.

Silfverberg et al. (2016) present two approaches for this problem, both relying on finite-state technology. In one approach, “unstructured,” they extract finite-state rules from pairs of strings and then apply them during decoding. In the “structured” case there is an additional Perceptron layer which is trained based on features extracted from the unstructured classifier. In addition, they have an additional layer which relies on a lexicon to find the best correction for a given input string.

Results Table 3 gives the results. We see that all uses of sequence labeling significantly outperform the results of Silfverberg et al. (2016). Even with an external lexicon, the results of the unstructured and structured classifiers of Silfverberg et al. significantly lag behind our results. Our results are also relatively stable with regards to word length. While the results are slightly lower for words of length 10 or more, the accuracy level is rather stable for other lengths. This is actually a different finding than the one we found with the Twitter spelling correction experiment. We see yet again that seq2seq modeling performs worse than our approach with biLSTM. seq2seq do not perform well with the hard monotonic attention model. This is on par with the results for the Twitter spelling dataset, on which we see bad behavior on long words. The OCR dataset indeed includes relatively long words.

4.3 Morphological Inflection

We also run experiments on the morphological inflection dataset used by Rastogi et al. (2016).⁵ This dataset was first processed by Dreyer (2011) and we use the same setup in our experiments, i.e., in each experiment we use the same 2,500 example dataset sampled from the CELEX database (Baayen et al., 1993) divided into three sets, 500 examples for training, and 1,000 for both development and testing. This

⁵https://github.com/se4u/neural_wfst/.

Model	13SIA	2PIE	2PKE	rP
biLSTM-WFST	85.1	94.4	85.5	83.0
biLSTM (ensemble)	85.8	94.6	86.0	83.8
Moses15	85.3	94.0	82.8	70.8
Dreyer (Backoff)	82.8	88.7	74.7	69.9
Dreyer (Lat-Class)	84.8	93.6	75.7	81.8
Dreyer (Lat-Region)	87.5	93.4	87.4	84.9
Kann (MED)	82.3	94.4	86.8	83.9
Kann (MED+POET)	83.9	95.0	87.6	84.0
seq2seq	83.1	93.8	88	83.2
seq2seq (hard)	85.8	95.1	89.5	87.2
EM	68.5	93.5	77.2	75.8
biLSTM (ours)	80.2	93.8	84.2	83.0
CRF	79.2	88.1	72.4	84.7
Spectral	81.9	94.0	83.2	83.8
Spectral (ensemble)	84.0	93.8	83.7	83.5
Spectral (oracle)	85.8	99.6	92.4	87.5

Table 4: Results on the morphological inflection datasets. Baselines (upper part of the table) are reported by Rastogi et al. (2016) and Dreyer (2011). The best result in each column is in bold. Results for seq2seq are reported by Aharoni and Goldberg (2017). Kann results are reported by Kann and Schütze (2016).

corpus is divided in four subsets, each defining an inflection task between different verb tenses in German. These are labeled as follows:

- 13SIA→13SKE - 1st/3rd persons singular of the indicative past to 1st/3rd persons singular of the subjunctive present.
- 2PIE→13PKE - 2nd person plural of the indicative present to 1st/3rd person plural of the subjunctive present.
- 2PKE→z - 2nd person plural of the subjunctive present to the infinitive.
- rP→pA - imperative plural to the past participle.

Further Tuning For the 13SIA dataset, we discovered on development data (fold 1) that the best context function is one that adds a single ε any time it appeared in the training data with a context $a\varepsilon b$. For 2PIE, we discovered similarly that adding a single ε is best in all cases it appears in the end of the word in the training set. Finally, for 2PKE and rP, we discovered the best context function is such that it adds a single ε or a pair of ε in any context it appears in the training data (with a character to the left and a character to the right).

The morphological inflection dataset is the most different of the three datasets mostly because it allows for the insertion or deletion of full suffixes. We speculate it is the main factor as to why the best context functions for the morphological datasets are different than for the previous two datasets (Twitter and OCR).

With the biLSTM model we discovered on the development set of the first fold of each dataset that: 13SIA works best with 2 layers of size 300; 2PIE works best with 1 layer of size 150; 2PKE works best with 1 layer of size 250; and rP-pA works best with 2 layers of size 250.

Results The results are in Table 4. The biLSTM results reported in the upper part of the table do not use our sequence labeling technique, and are re-iterated as reported by Rastogi et al. (2016).

In general, the spectral algorithm does not perform as well as the LSTM baseline with finite state transducers, but does better than it on the rP-pA dataset. The spectral algorithm performs significantly better than some of the other baselines, such as Moses or the baselines from Dreyer (2011). This is especially true for the 2PKE and the rP-pA datasets.

An additional observation is that the way we handle insertions has a significant impact on the performance. In oracle mode (meaning, when the two strings are aligned using edit distance even at decoding time, and the spurious insertions are not used), the spectral algorithm performs significantly better. This should not come as a surprise, but does point to a direction on how to improve the use of our sequence labeling technique – better handling of insertions and the addition of less spurious insertion placeholders that are deleted during decoding.

In contrast to the other datasets, where perhaps the assumption of monotonicity is too strong, seq2seq models with an attention mechanism designed to handle monotonic alignments (Aharoni and Goldberg, 2017) perform quite well on this task, even better than the vanilla seq2seq models.

Finally, we also consider the case in which we use an ensemble method, combining several spectral models together (the top 50 performing models on the development set from the hyperparameter sweep). We combine the models using a MaxEnt reranker such as described by Charniak and Johnson (2005) and Narayan and Cohen (2015). We find that the ensemble approach does improve the results significantly for the 13SIA dataset, and also for the 2PKE-z dataset.

5 Conclusion

We presented a technique to frame general string transduction problems as sequence labeling. Our technique works by adding to the string to be transduced additional insertion markers, which are later potentially deleted during the sequence labeling process. Our approach is general and works with any sequence labeling algorithm. We developed our technique with conditional random fields, refinement hidden Markov models and neural networks. We tested our approach on problems from three challenging domains: spelling correction for social media, optical character recognition correction and morphological inflection. We demonstrated that our approach performs comparably to strong baselines and state of the art.

While the idea of using redundant epsilons in string transduction problems has been used in the past (Azawi et al., 2013; Schnober et al., 2016), it has traditionally been treated in an ad-hoc narrow manner, for example by adding a fixed number of epsilons after every character. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to rigorously define this idea as a learning problem while performing a comprehensive empirical evaluation for it, both with respect to the type of datasets used and the sequence labeling algorithms covered.

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